
**ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ АЦЕТОНОФОРМАЛЬДЕГИДНЫХ СМОЛ В КАЧЕСТВЕ
ДОБАВКИ К БЕТОНУ.**

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Аннотация.

В статье, предложена пластифицирующих и пластифицирующе-воздухововлекающих добавок в производстве сборных и монолитных железобетонных изделий и конструкций позволит повысить их качество, снизить трудозатраты и расход цемента.

Ключевые слова.

добавок, сборных, качество, заполнитель, монолит, бетонная смесь;

APPLICATION OF ACETONE FORMALDEHYDE RESINS AS AN

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Аннотация.

The article proposes plasticizing and plasticizing-air-entraining additives in the production of precast and monolithic reinforced concrete products and structures will improve their quality, reduce labor costs and cement consumption.

Keywords.

additives, prefabricated, quality, aggregate, monolith, concrete mix;

The use of the proposed plasticizing and plasticizing-air-entraining additives in the production of prefabricated and monolithic reinforced concrete products and structures will improve their quality, reduce labor costs and cement consumption [2.5.3].

To concrete on dense aggregates in the manufacture of monolithic and prefabricated reinforced concrete products and structures, hardening in air-dry, humid and heat-humid conditions, in order to:

- a) reducing the consumption of cement;
- b) increasing the mobility and viability, improving the workability, uniformity and non-separation of the concrete mixture;
- c) regulation of the terms of loss of mobility in time at different ambient temperatures, the speed of the processes of setting, hardening and heat generation;
- d) reducing the duration of the manufacture of products, heat treatment of concrete, accelerating the timing of its stripping and loading with natural curing;
- e) increasing the density, strength and frost resistance of concrete [26].

Resin additives are recommended to be introduced into the mixing water during the preparation of a concrete mixture, both in the usual technology and in two and three-stage sequences of preparation using turbulent mixers. SAFA resin additive should be used to obtain a plasticizing and air-entraining effect and to preserve the mobility of the concrete mixture. Regardless of the composition of the initial concrete mix and concrete grade, before the practical use of additives, the concrete composition should be adjusted for water demand, cement consumption and other components [3].

SAFA resin is a product of the composition of concrete, technology of concrete with additives, quality control of concrete with additives, safety and labor protection when using acetone-formaldehyde resins, as well as an example of adjusting the composition of concrete with additives and the main indicators of an aqueous solution in additives is carried out according to [6.7].

The ACF-3M resin additive should be added in an amount of 0.1-0.2% of the cement mass in terms of dry matter. In this case, the maximum strength effect is achieved at 0.15% additive. The resulting increase in strength can be used in the future to reduce the consumption of cement or the duration of heat treatment.

To increase mobility, air entrainment and reduce cement consumption, it is recommended to introduce SAFA resin additive in quantities 0.1-0.15% by weight of cement in terms of dry matter. To ensure the conservation of the mobility of the concrete mixture, SAFA resin modified with furfuryl should be used in an amount of 0.2-0.3% by weight of cement in terms of dry matter. [1.4.8].

It is recommended to adjust the composition of concrete with the addition of ACF-3M resin as follows:

a) prepare the initial composition of the concrete mixture without additives and with 0.15% resin, determine the mobility of the concrete mixture, make six samples - cubes with an edge of 100 mm, withstand three samples under normal hardening conditions for 28 days, and three are subjected to heat and moisture treatment, then test them. As a result, establish an increase in mobility and strength;

reduce the cement content and water consumption until an equally mobile concrete mixture is obtained. At the same time, simultaneously with the mobility of the concrete mixture, determine concrete samples and, as a result, establish the water demand of the concrete mixture with the additive.

c) according to the adjusted water demand, refine the consumption of cement by reducing its amount to such a value at which the design grade of the initial concrete composition will be achieved;

d) according to the laboratory adjustment of the composition of concrete with an additive, clarify the quantitative content of the constituent components and establish the amount of cement savings;

Adjustment of the composition of concrete with dovaky SAFA resin should be made in accordance with the addition of ACF-3M, supplementing the tests with the determination of the volumetric mass of the concrete mixture. At the same time, the mobility, volumetric mass of the mixture and the strength of concrete are determined at different mixing times of the concrete mixture and set the duration of the preparation of the mixture, at which the required air content of concrete is achieved. [3.2].

When using the SAFA resin modified with furfural, the adjustment of the concrete mixture with the additive consists in determining its quantitative content, water demand and concrete strength to ensure the design composition and the required conservation indicators of the mobility of the concrete mixture.

Technology of concrete with ACF and SAFA additives. The preparation of a concrete mixture with additives with the introduction of ACF resins into mixing water can be carried out by the usual, two and three-layer method. The two-stage preparation method consists in the dosage of the constituent components, mixing water with an additive in cement, followed by mixing the binder with a dry mixture of sand and gravel (gravel). The three-stage method of preparation is different in that the binder is first mixed with sand and then with shabn (gravel). [4.6].

Conclusions: In order to limit water entrainment in each specific case, it is recommended to experimentally determine the duration of the movement of the concrete mixture with the addition of ACF resins.

Additives of ACF resins can be introduced directly into the mixing water, or they can be pre-prepared in aqueous solutions of 5-10% concentration. The consumption of ACF resin additives when directly introduced into the mixing water can be determined by the formula:

$$A = \frac{C \cdot K}{100}$$

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K

where: A is the consumption of the additive for one batch of concrete mix, kg;

C-consumption of cement for one batch, kg;

C is the dosage of the additive,% of the mass of cement;

K is the concentration of dry matter in the resin.

LITERATURE:

1. Gromakovskiy K.F. Agricultural use of synthetic fatty acids. "Oil and fat industry", 2003, No. 1, pp. 38-39

2. Bazhenov Yu.M. concrete technology. M, High School. 2002 pp. 20, 40,

3. Djurayevna T. N. et al. Building Materials Determined In The Architectural Monuments Of Central Asia //The American Journal of Applied sciences. - 2020. - Vol. 2. - No. 12. - S. 77-80.

4. Mamazonov A. U., Teshaboeva N. D. USE OF MINERAL FILLERS AND CHEMICAL ADDITIVES ACP, PAV POLYFUNCTIONAL PURPOSE, IN THE PRODUCTION OF CEMENT, MONOLITHIC AND PREFACED REINFORCED CONCRETE STRUCTURES //Eurasian Union of Scientists. – 2020.-no. 3-2

5.Teshaboeva N.D. Influence of the drying up of the Aral Sea and dry hot climate of Central Asia on load-bearing and enclosing structures and buildings and structures. young scientist. no. 20. (258). May 2019.

6. Djurayevna T. N. et al. Building Materials Determined In The Architectural Monuments Of Central Asia //The American Journal of Applied sciences. - 2020. - Vol. 2. - No. 12. - S. 77-80.

7. Teshaboeva N.D. Influence Of Surface Additives On Strength Indicators Of Cement Systems. The American Journal of Applied Sciences. IMPACT FACTOR 2020: 5.276.

8. Teshaboeva N.D. Building materials, standards, laboratory conditions, natural and climate conditions. The American journal of applied sciences.2020. 5.276

9. Teshaboeva N. D. BUILDING MATERIALS DETERMINED IN THE ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS OF CENTRAL ASIA //Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. - 2023. - T. 11. - No. 2. - S. 214-217.

10. Djurayevna T. N. Influence Of Surface Additives On Strength Indicators Of Cement Systems // The American Journal of Applied sciences. - 2020. - Vol. 2. - No. 12. - S. 81-85.

11. Djuraevna T. N. Strength Indicators Of Cement Systems With Additives Of Surface-Active Substances // The American Journal of Applied sciences. - 2021. - Vol. 3. - No. 5. - S. 203-209.

12. Djuraevna T. N. Effect of chemical additives on the construction-technical properties of concrete mixture // ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. - 2020. - T. 10. - No. 5. - S. 809-812.

13. Mamazhonov A.U., Teshaboeva N.D. INFLUENCE OF DISPERSITY AND QUANTITY OF MINERAL FILLER ON CEMENT PARTICLES AUTOHESIA //Eurasian Union of Scientists. - 2019. - no. 12-4(69). - P. 7-10.